

Table 1. Atmospheric temperature, rainfall, and solar radiation during planting time. Nainital, U. P., India, 1985 wet season.

Date	Temperature (°C)		Rainfall (mm)	Sunshine (h/d)
	Maximum	Minimum		
18-24 Jun	40.0	27.7	26.4	6.7
25- 1 Jun	35.1	24.7	48.7	8.8
2- 8 Jul	33.2	25.4	54.4	5.3
9-15 Jul	31.1	24.7	113.0	5.5
16-22 Jul	31.1	24.6	129.9	6.1

243.8 m altitude), we used Beni silty clay loam, fine-silty, mixed, hyperthermic, Aquic Hapludoll with pH 7.5, 1.3% organic C, 0.11% total N, 15.82 kg available (Olsen) P/ha, and 139.68 kg available K/ha. The region enjoys subhumid subtropical climate with high temperature in May-Jun and heavy rainfall during Jul-Aug (Table 1). Twelve treatment combinations—three

planting dates, two varieties and two N rates—were compared in a randomized block design (Table 2). Varieties Govind and Pant Dhan 4 differed in duration (105 and 130 d).

Significantly higher grain yield was obtained with early planting, high N, and with a short-duration variety under delayed planting. □

Table 2. Grain yield as influenced by planting date, variety, and N rate. Nainital, India, 1985 wet season.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)
<i>Planting date</i> ^a	
25 Jun	5.4
5 Jul	4.8
15 Jul	3.9
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.3
<i>Variety</i>	
Pant Dhan 4	4.2
Govind	5.2
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.2
<i>N rate (kg/ha)</i>	
60	4.4
120	5.0
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.2
CV (%)	7.8

^aSeed sowing date in nursery.

Soil fertility and fertilizer management

Effect of N source and application time on rice

N. A. Salam, E. Tajuddin, K. Varghese, S. M. S. Hameed, and Y. Thomas, Kerala Agricultural University, Karamana 695002, Trivandrum, India

We studied effects of N sources and application times on Jaya rice grain and straw yields during 1987 kharif (Jun-Sep) at the Cropping Systems Research

Center, Trivandrum (11°N, 77°E, 30 m above mean sea level). We used 3 sources of N at 90 kg N/ha and 4 application times (see table). The basal application was broadcast and incorporated at transplanting time. For topdressing, all sources were broadcast, keeping soil moist and gradually increasing the water level to 2-3 cm. The soil (sandy clay loam, riverine alluvium deposited over laterite soil) contained 0.47% organic C, 120-7.7-58 ppm of

available NPK, and 390 ppm total soil N, with a pH of 5.2 and EC of 0.25 dS/m.

Results show N impact differed with source and with application time. PU gave higher grain (14% moisture) and straw yields when applied in 3 splits (1/3 basal + 1/3 at tillering + 1/3 at panicle initiation). MPCU should be applied entirely as basal or in 2 splits (1/2 basal + 1/2 at tillering). LGU gave best yields when applied in 2 splits (1/2 basal + 1/2 at tillering) or in 3 splits (1/2 basal + 1/4 at tillering + 1/4 at panicle initiation). □

Grain and straw yields as influenced by time of application and source^a of urea. Trivandrum, India, Jun-Sep, 1987.

Time ^b	Grain yield (t/ha)				Straw yield (t/ha)				
	PU	MPCU	LGU	Mean	PU	MPCU	LGU	Mean	
Full basal	3.0	3.4	3.0	3.1	4.2	4.1	5.0	4.5	
1/2 B + 1/2 T	3.0	3.5	3.7	3.4	6.3	5.1	5.6	5.6	
1/2 B + 1/4 T + 1/4 PI	2.6	2.6	3.7	3.0	4.4	5.6	5.7	5.2	
1/3 B + 1/3 T + 1/3 PI	3.3	2.9	2.7	3.0	4.9	4.6	4.0	4.5	
	3.0	3.1	3.3		4.9	4.8	5.1		
	LSD (0.05)				LSD (0.05)				
Time (T)				0.3	Time (T)				0.5
Source (S)				ns	Source (S)				ns
T × S				0.5	T × S				0.9

^aPU = prilled urea, MPCU = Mussoorie phosphate-coated urea, LGU = large granule urea. ^bB = basal, T = tillering, PI = panicle initiation.

Estimation of pH, ammonium N, and nitrate N of floodwater with integrated N management of lowland rice

B. S. Mahapatra, K. C. Sharma, and G. L. Sharma Agronomy Department, G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar, Nainital 263145, U.P., India

Ammonium N and nitrate N in floodwater reflect the N loss that occurs easily in a submerged soil-water system common to lowland rice. The extent of

ammonium N in floodwater is controlled by the pH of floodwater.

We measured the pH, ammonium N, and nitrate N of floodwater with integrated organic-inorganic N management. The experimental loam soil (Mollisol of Tarai of northern India) had pH (1:1) 7.6, EC (1:1) 0.115 dS/m, 2.03% organic C, 0.21% total N, 7.4 ppm available ammonium N, and 12.2 ppm available NO₃⁻-N

Floodwater ammonium N peaked at 3 d after transplanting (DT) in 1982-83 and at 7 DT in 1983-84. Thereafter, it decreased and was not found in either year at 30 DT (see figure).

The low concentration of floodwater ammonium N is attributed to floodwater pH, in turn controlled by partial pressure of CO₂. Higher concentration of ammonium N in 1983-84 over 1982-83 is also attributed to floodwater pH, as pH at the initial dates after transplanting was higher in 1983-84 (see figure).

Nitrate N peaked at 9 DT and

Floodwater pH, NH₄⁺-N, and NO₃⁻-N with respect to time in lowland rice. Nainital, U.P., India.

reached zero at 30 DT both years. However, its concentration was more than that of ammonium N, probably because of nitrification in the transitional zone of the flooded soil water system.

Results show that floodwater pH, ammonium N, and nitrate N can be kept at lower levels by using organic N sources (green manure and farmyard manure) as part of integrated N management. □

Efficiency of modified urea granules in transplanted rice

T. V. R. Prasad, M. M. Hosmani, L. S. Devi, and K. R. Kulkarni, Agronomic Research Project, University of Agricultural Sciences, GKVK, Bangalore 560065, India

We tested efficiency of modified urea granules in transplanted rice in farmers' fields, Bangalore district, Karnataka, India, in monsoon 1986.

Seven treatments (see table) were tried

in 10 randomly selected fields, using cultivar Mandya Vani (140-d duration) in clay to clay loam soils. The soils had pH 6.6, EC of 0.18 dS/m at 25 °C, 489 kg available N/ha, 14.2 kg P/ha, and 285.4 kg K/ha. A common dose of 22 kg P and 42 kg K/ha was applied in a plot 50 m².

At 56 kg N/ha, urea supergranule (USG) was superior (29.6% more yield), followed by rock phosphate-coated urea (RPCU, 24.2%), large urea granule (LGU, 18.6%), and gypsum-coated urea

(GCU, 16.7%). Modified urea granules may provide more efficient N utilization, shown by higher harvest index (ratio of yield to total biomass), more panicles per m² at harvest, and more filled grains per panicle (see table).

In yield per kg of added N, USG was best, followed by RPCU, LGU, and GCU, all superior to prilled urea (PU) at 56 and 84 kg N/ha. Cost-wise, PU equals LGU, with others equal to or 10-20% higher than PU. □

Effect of modified urea granules on grain yield and yield attributes.^a Bangalore, India, 1986 wet season.

Treatment ^b	Grain yield (t/ha)	Response ^c (kg grain/kg N)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Filled grains/panicle	Harvest index	Biomass (t/ha)
T1 No N	3.60 g	—	14.3 g	97 cde	0.44 e	8.5 g
T2 PU ^d	4.51 f	16.2	89.3 f	101 cd	0.46 d	10.3 f
T3 LGU (45% N) ^e	5.35 bcd	31.2	105.9 abc	121 a	0.48 c	11.3 abc
T4 RPCU (36.4% N, 1.85% P) ^e	5.60 abc	35.7	109.4 a	103 c	0.52 a	11.0 abcde
T5 GCU (36.5% N, 4.4% Ca, 3.4% S) ^e	5.26 de	29.6	103.8 abcd	115 ab	0.48 c	11.1 abcd
T6 USG (45% N) ^f	5.85 a	40.1	108.0 ab	121 a	0.52 a	11.4 ab
T7 PU ^d	5.63 ab	24.2	101.3 cde	121 a	0.50 b	11.6 a

^aColumn means followed by common letters are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bT2 - T6 at 56 kg N/ha, T7 at 84 kg N/ha. ^cOver 0 kg N/ha. ^dApplied in 3 equal splits: basal, 30 and 50 d after transplanting. ^eBasal broadcast incorporation. ^fPlacement after planting.